

Supporting information

Effective monitoring of freshwater fish

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Supporting Information S1

Monitoring reflected in scientific articles

A literature search with the Web of Science (Fig. S1.1) shows that: i) freshwater fish are an important, traditional part of papers dealing with monitoring, similarly to birds and more than butterflies; ii) some topics such as “data management” seem less dealt with regard to monitoring; and iii) other topics related to monitoring such as environmental DNA and citizen-science emerged very recently and are increasingly popular.

Figure S1.1. Historical variation in the number of publications on monitoring and related topics according to a literature search in the Web of Science. The search was performed on 27 February 2018 (but excludes papers published in 2018) using “Science Citation Index Expanded” (topics: monitoring” and freshwater fish*” or “bird*” or “butterfl*” or data management” or “adaptive” or “citizen-science” or “environmental DNA”). Notice the logarithmic scale in the number of publications and that the Web of Science started to systematically include the abstracts of papers in 1990, hence producing a general increase that year.

Table S1.1. Examples of definitions and major purposes of monitoring in the context of conservation and ecology (CE) in general, and of aquatic sciences (e.g. (FE) fish ecology, (WQ) water quality).

Definition and/or major purpose	Context	Source
Monitoring is purpose orientated; it tells us how something(s) is/are changing; it is repeated at regular intervals and it often provides the baseline for recording possible change in the future	CE	Goldsmith (1991)
Repeated field-based empirical measurements are collected continuously and then analyzed for at least 10 years	CE	Lindenmayer & Likens (2010)
... to document changes in biodiversity over time	CE	Mihoub <i>et al.</i> (2017)
... acquiring information needed to improve management decisions [in relation to] adaptive management [...] and to inform state-dependent management	CE	McDonald-Madden <i>et al.</i> (2010)
... provides the principal record of [long-term] change	CE	Lovett <i>et al.</i> (2007)
... assessing the condition of a habitat or species against a predetermined standard	CE	Hurford, Schneider, & Cowx (2010)
... long-term assessment of populations and communities	FE	Wildhaber <i>et al.</i> (2011)
... to assess [a] status in relation to [its] overall conservation objectives and management prescriptions	FE	Cowx <i>et al.</i> (2009)
... provide information that assesses the response of large river resources to management practices	FE	Counihan <i>et al.</i> (2018)
... to provide a system that would generate sufficient and timely information to enable the managers to make informed management decisions	WQ	Telci <i>et al.</i> (2009)
... acquisition of quantitative and representative information on [...] characteristics of a water body over time and space	WQ	Strobl & Robillard (2008)

Supporting Information S2

Monitoring vs survey vs surveillance

The need for a clear aims (and even guidance by a priori hypotheses) (Nichols & Williams, 2006) distinguishes monitoring from other data collection efforts such as surveys and surveillance (also called surveillance monitoring) (Tables S2.1 and S2.2). More specifically, surveillance often focuses on short-term measurements and/or lacks rigour and standards in data collection or a question-driven design, which is analogous to the curiosity-driven or passive monitoring described by Lindenmayer & Likens (2009, 2010). Surveillance has been vigorously criticized in favour of question-driven monitoring due to its lack of hypotheses that leads to poor experimental design and inability to identify the drivers of change (Nichols & Williams, 2006; Lindenmayer & Likens, 2009, 2010).

Table S2.1. Comparison of survey, surveillance and monitoring (in the strict sense) in some key references.

	Survey	Surveillance	Monitoring
Hellawell (1991)	“An exercise in which a set of qualitative or quantitative observations are made, usually by means of a standardised procedure and within a restricted period of time, but without any preconception of what the findings ought to be.”	“An extended programme of surveys, undertaken in order to provide a time series, to ascertain the variability and/or range of states or values which might be encountered over time (but again without preconceptions of what these might be).”	“Intermittent (regular or irregular) surveillance carried out in order to ascertain the extent of compliance with a predetermined standard or the degree of deviation from an expected norm.”
Nichols & Williams (2006)		“By surveillance monitoring, we mean monitoring that is not guided by a priori hypotheses and their corresponding models.”	“Targeted [or focused] monitoring is defined by its integration into conservation practice, with monitoring design and implementation based on a priori hypotheses and associated models of system responses to management.”
Alexander (2009)	“Making a single observation to measure and record something.”	“Making repeated standardised surveys in order that change can be detected. This is quite different to, but often confused with, monitoring. Surveillance lacks the formulated standards that are so important in monitoring. Surveillance is used to detect change but does not differentiate between acceptable and unacceptable change.”	“Surveillance undertaken to ensure that formulated standards are being maintained (JNCC 1998). Monitoring should be an essential and integral component of management planning: there can be no planning without monitoring and no monitoring without planning. Monitoring projects should not be unnecessarily complicated. A decision must be made about how accurate a monitoring project needs to be.”
Hurford <i>et al.</i> (2010)	“a set of standard observations, usually obtained with a standard method and within a restricted time period, typically a one-off exercise, e.g. mapping a habitat or compiling a species list.”	“typically, a series of repeat surveys used to detect or track trends of habitats or species. Differs from monitoring by not measuring against a predetermined standard.”	“for the purposes of this book, monitoring is defined as assessing the condition of a habitat or species against a predetermined standard.”

Table S2.2. Examples of specific aims of fish monitoring.

Aim	Reference
Monitoring of ...	
... species richness and diversity of the assemblage	Oberdorff, Guégan, & Hugueny (1995); Coughlan <i>et al.</i> (2018)
... fish community composition and associated biometrics	Jackson, Peres-Neto, & Olden (2001); Lohner & Dixon (2013)
... biological/ecological integrity	Pont <i>et al.</i> (2006); Jurajda <i>et al.</i> (2010)
... population-specific metrics relating to species of conservation importance (e.g. imperilled native species, high-risk invasive species)	Maxwell & Jennings, 2005; Cowx <i>et al.</i> (2010); Lundqvist <i>et al.</i> (2010); Cooke <i>et al.</i> (2012); Van Haverbeke <i>et al.</i> (2013)
... specific life-stages of single or multiple species (e.g. larval and juvenile stages)	Cowx, Nunn, & Harvey (2001)
... population dynamics of species	Elliott (1984); Wildhaber <i>et al.</i> (2011)
... age structure and recruitment and population dynamics of single or multiple species	Nunn <i>et al.</i> (2007)
... population genetic structure	Heath <i>et al.</i> (2002)
... community and/or population trophic dynamics	Bašić & Britton (2016)
... fisheries stocks	Mann & Welton (1995); Lundqvist <i>et al.</i> (2010); FAO (2016)
... environmental pollution and water quality	Hesthagen <i>et al.</i> (1995); Ozmen <i>et al.</i> (2006); Southworth <i>et al.</i> (2011); Barrett <i>et al.</i> (2015)
... fish kills	Trim & Marcus (1990); Burkholder (2001)
... effects of ecosystem and habitat alteration	Kristensen, Baattrup-Pedersen, & Andersen (2012); Mueller, Pander, & Geist (2014); Radinger <i>et al.</i> (2016); Colloff <i>et al.</i> (2018)
... wetland evaluation	Bravo-Utrera (2010); Kaller, Kelso, & Trexler (2013)
... dynamics of native species	Cowx & Fraser (2003); Harvey <i>et al.</i> , 2010; West (2010)
... dynamics of alien species	Vilà & García-Berthou (2010); Bylemans <i>et al.</i> (2016); Janáč <i>et al.</i> (2018)

Table S2.3. Main stages in designing a monitoring programme (based on: Goldsmith, 1991; Hellawell, 1991; Bisbal, 2001; Scardi, Tancioni, & Cataudella, 2006; Strobl & Robillard, 2008; Hurford, 2010; Rowell, 2010; Lindenmayer & Likens, 2010)

Problem Identification: A monitoring programme begins with simple problems or questions raised by scientists, stakeholders or managers.

Research Questions: What are the questions to be answered by the monitoring?

Theory and Existing Information: Identification of the most likely causes of the problem requires examination of existing information in the context of relevant theories and concepts.

Predictions, Hypotheses, and Aims: Integration of the questions, existing information and theory allows formulating predictions that can be restated as objectives or testable research hypotheses.

The Data Statement: It defines the data needed to reach the aims. It specifies the sampling procedure to be used, the measurements to be made and the study design.

Planning for Sampling: The particulars of the data statement, the characteristics of the sampled population and the available budget exert strong influence on the sampling design.

Preparing for Sampling: Development of a data management plan to ensure that collected data are interpretable, organized, and accessible for analysis. Decide exactly how data will be recorded in the field. Hire the best personnel identifying potential obstacles to successful completion of the study (floods, drought, accidents, equipment failure, etc.). Acquisition of equipment and supplies is often the final step before sampling.

Sample Collection and Processing: Efficient sampling requires an organized crew of adequate size.

Data Analysis: Data analysis concludes with realization of the results of the study. Results state the findings of the study in the context of the aims or hypotheses. Evaluation entails critical and objective assessment of the study. Do any concerns exist that cast doubt on the validity of the study? Was it conducted competently and as planned? Did deviations from the study plan occur? Were the prescribed samples collected? Did they provide the necessary data? Were the sample sizes adequate? Was precision adequate? Do unintentional biases exist?

Synthesis and Inference: Synthesis integrates the findings with existing information (e.g. reference sites) and inference assesses the applicability of the findings beyond the specific scope of the study.

Communication of Results

Supporting Information S3

Sampling design in freshwater fish monitoring

The spatial distribution of the sampling sites should match the monitoring aims(s) (Dixon & Chiswell, 1996). The heterogeneous, hierarchically structured characteristics of aquatic environments, such as river drainages (Lowe, Likens, & Power, 2006; Thorp, Thoms, & Delong, 2006), often limits the application of simple random sampling for monitoring and can make their sampling more difficult than in lake ecosystems (Downes *et al.*, 2002). The effect of spatial variability is reduced by stratified random sampling, i.e. the proportional sampling of strata that represent different habitat units (Quinn & Keough, 2002; Conroy & Carroll, 2009; García-Berthou *et al.*, 2009) and is widely used in aquatic ecosystems (Wilde & Fisher, 1996; Dukerschein *et al.*, 2011; Haxton, 2011). In a systematic sampling design, the first sampling is chosen at random and all subsequent samplings are regularly placed in space or time (Quinn & Keough, 2002; Conroy & Carroll, 2009). A systematic design is useful, such as to investigate effects of environmental gradients. A recent development is the Generalized Random Tessellation Stratified design (GRTS) (Stevens & Olsen, 2003, 2004; Kincaid & Olsen, 2016), which allows design-based inferences to entire areas and is approximately spatially-balanced (i.e. no sites in the target population are too far from each other and few sampled sites are close together).

Quantitative methods to optimize the network design are increasingly addressed in surface and ground water quality (Telci *et al.*, 2009; Behmel *et al.*, 2016) and conservation planning (Possingham *et al.*, 2000) but have been seldom applied to freshwater fish monitoring.

In fish monitoring, sampling sites are frequently selected non-randomly, often based on judgment or convenience (Wilde & Fisher, 1996; Pope, Lochmann, & Young, 2010). In this context, McClelland & Sass (2012) compared fixed and random sampling for boat electrofishing and concluded that although fixed site sampling may provide more and a greater diversity of fishes, random site selection is unbiased and may provide greater spatial coverage. However, it is recommended to continuously re-evaluate the effort allocation as data are gathered and its variability analysed, i.e. it requires an adaptive approach (Larsen *et al.*, 2001), and a potential re-design of the sampling effort to account for any changes in chemical, physical or biological conditions (Strobl & Robillard, 2008; Buckland *et al.*, 2012).

Supporting Information S4

Fish monitoring protocols

Table S4.1. Examples of fish monitoring protocols. Sampling methods: (E) electrofishing, (N) netting (e.g. gillnets), (T) trapping (e.g. fyke nets, minnow traps), (H) hydroacoustics, (O) other methods (e.g. spotlighting)

Continent	Country	Title	Method	Env.	Other aspects	Link
North America		Standard methods for sampling North American freshwater fishes	multiple including E, N, H, T	lotic, lentic	overview on standard sampling	https://fisheriesstandardsampling.org/content/about-standard-sampling
North America	USA	Standard fish sampling protocol for lowland lakes and reservoirs in Idaho	E,N,T	lentic	sampling design & site selection	https://collaboration.idfg.idaho.gov/FisheriesTechnicalReports/Res12-10Lamansky2012%20Lake%20and%20Reservoir%20Sampling%20Protocol.pdf
North America	USA	Fish community sampling protocol for stream monitoring sites	E	lotic	data reporting	https://www.pca.state.mn.us/sites/default/files/sf-sop-fish.pdf
North America	USA	General protocol for sport fish sampling and analysis	unspecific	unspecific	assessing chemical components in fish tissue samples, sampling design	https://oehha.ca.gov/media/downloads/fish/document/fishsamplingprotocol2005.pdf

Continent	Country	Title	Method	Env.	Other aspects	Link
North America	USA	Rapid Bioassessment Protocols for Use in Streams and Wadeable Rivers: Periphyton, Benthic Macroinvertebrates, and Fish	E	lotic	fish-based bioassessment, sampling procedures, quality control	https://archive.epa.gov/water/archive/web/html/ch08main.html
		Lake fisheries sampling protocol	E, N, T	lentic	sampling procedure, data reporting	http://files.dep.state.pa.us/Water/Drinking%20Water%20and%20Facility%20Regulation/WaterQualityPortalFiles/Methodology/2015%20Methodology/Lake%20Fisheries%20Sampling%20Protocol.pdf
North America	Canada	Manual of Instructions and Provincial Biodiversity Benchmark Values - NORDIC Index Netting	N	lentic	sampling design, sampling procedure, data reporting and management	http://www3.laurentian.ca/livingwithlakes/wp-content/uploads/2012/06/Nordic-Index-Netting.pdf
North America	Canada	Methods for monitoring fish populations	N,E,T	lotic, lentic	overview on multiple guidelines, sampling procedures, data reporting and processing	https://www.ontario.ca/page/methods-monitoring-fish-populations
Europe	Europe	STARFISH sampling protocol	E	lotic	fish welfare, parameters to record, site selection	http://www.eu-star.at/pdf/FishSamplingProtocol.pdf

Continent	Country	Title	Method	Env.	Other aspects	Link
Europe	European Standard	DIN EN 14757 Water quality - Sampling of fish with multi-mesh gillnets	N	lotic, lentic	sampling design, data handling and analysis	https://www.en-standard.eu/din-en-14757-water-quality-sampling-of-fish-with-multi-mesh-gillnets/
Europe	European Standard	CSN EN 15910 Water quality - Guidance on the estimation of fish abundance with mobile hydroacoustic methods	H	lotic, lentic	sampling design, data handling & analysis	https://www.en-standard.eu/csn-en-15910-water-quality-guidance-on-the-estimation-of-fish-abundance-with-mobile-hydroacoustic-methods/
Europe	European Standard	DIN EN 14011 Water quality - Sampling of fish with electricity	E	lotic, lentic	applicability, safety, data & reporting	https://www.en-standard.eu/din-en-14011-water-quality-sampling-of-fish-with-electricity/
Oceania	New Zealand	New Zealand freshwater fish sampling protocols	E,T,O	lotic	sampling design, method selection, fish welfare, safety, data handling & analysis	https://www.niwa.co.nz/static/web/New_Zealand_Freshwater_Fish_Sampling_Protocols.pdf
Oceania	Australia	Monitoring and Sampling Manual 2009	N,T,E	lotic, lentic	sampling design & site selection, water quality parameters	https://www.ehp.qld.gov.au/water/pdf/monitoring-man-2009-v2.pdf
Oceania	Australia	Fisheries Long Term Monitoring Program Sampling Protocol	E	lotic	site selection	https://www.daf.qld.gov.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0004/58270/Freshwater-Summary-2000.pdf

Supporting Information – References

- ALEXANDER, M. (2008) *Management Planning for Nature Conservation - A Theoretical Basis & Practical Guide*. Springer, Dordrecht.
- BARRETT, T.J., BRASFIELD, S.M., CARROLL, L.C., DOYLE, M.A., VAN DEN HEUVEL, M.R. & MUNKITTRICK, K.R. (2015) Reproductive strategies and seasonal changes in the somatic indices of seven small-bodied fishes in Atlantic Canada in relation to study design for environmental effects monitoring. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 187, 305.
- BAŠIĆ, T. & BRITTON, J.R. (2016) Characterizing the trophic niches of stocked and resident cyprinid fishes: consistency in partitioning over time, space and body sizes. *Ecology and Evolution* 6, 5093–5104.
- BEHME, S., DAMOUR, M., LUDWIG, R. & RODRIGUEZ, M.J. (2016) Water quality monitoring strategies – A review and future perspectives. *Science of The Total Environment* 571, 1312–1329.
- BISBAL, G.A. (2001) Conceptual Design of Monitoring and Evaluation Plans for Fish and Wildlife in the Columbia River Ecosystem. *Environmental Management* 28, 433–453.
- BRAVO-UTRERA, M.A. (2010) Monitoring aquatic ecosystems at Doana natural space. In *Conservation Monitoring in Freshwater Habitats* (eds C. HURFORD, M. SCHNEIDER & I. COWX), pp. 339–355. Springer, Dordrecht.
- BUCKLAND, S.T., BAILLIE, S.R., DICK, J.M., ELSTON, D.A., MAGURRAN, A.E., SCOTT, E.M., SMITH, R.I., SOMERFIELD, P.J., STUDENY, A.C. & WATT, A. (2012) How should regional biodiversity be monitored? *Environmental and Ecological Statistics* 19, 601–626.
- BURKHOLDER, J.M. (2001) Beyond algal blooms, oxygen deficits and fish kills: chronic, long-term impacts of nutrient pollution on aquatic ecosystems. In *Waters in Peril* (eds L. BENDELL-YOUNG & P. GALLAUGHER), pp. 103–125. Springer, Boston.
- BYLEMANS, J., FURLAN, E.M., PEARCE, L., DALY, T. & GLEESON, D.M. (2016) Improving the containment of a freshwater invader using environmental DNA (eDNA) based monitoring. *Biological Invasions* 18, 3081–3089.
- COLLOFF, M.J., OVERTON, I.C., HENDERSON, B.L., ROBERTS, J., REID, J.R.W., OLIVER, R.L., ARTHUR, A.D., DOODY, T.M., SIMS, N.C., YE, Q. & CUDDY, S.M. (2018) The use of historical environmental monitoring data to test predictions on cross-scale ecological responses to alterations in river flows. *Aquatic Ecology* 52, 133–153.
- CONROY, M.J. & CARROLL, J.P. (2009) *Quantitative Conservation of Vertebrates*. Wiley-Blackwell, Chichester, UK.
- COOKE, S., PAUKERT, C. & HOGAN, Z. (2012) Endangered river fish: factors hindering conservation and restoration. *Endangered Species Research* 17, 179–191.
- COUNIHAN, T.D., WAITE, I.R., CASPER, A.F., WARD, D.L., SAUER, J.S., IRWIN, E.R., CHAPMAN, C.G., ICKES, B.S., PAUKERT, C.P., KOSOVICH, J.J. & BAYER, J.M. (2018) Can data from disparate long-term fish monitoring programs be used to increase our understanding of regional and continental trends in large river assemblages? *PLoS One* 13, e0191472.
- COWX, I.G. & FRASER, D. (2003) Monitoring the Atlantic Salmon *Salmo Salar*. *Conserving Natura 2000 Rivers Monitoring Series* 7, 1–36.
- COWX, I.G., HARVEY, J.P., NOBLE, R.A. & NUNN, A.D. (2009) Establishing survey and monitoring protocols for the assessment of conservation status of fish populations in river Special Areas of Conservation in the UK. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 19, 96–103.
- COWX, I.G., HARVEY, J.P., NOBLE, R.A. & NUNN, A.D. (2010) Monitoring fish populations in river SACs. In *Conservation Monitoring in Freshwater Habitats* (eds C. HURFORD, M. SCHNEIDER & I. COWX), pp. 53–62. Springer, Dordrecht.
- COWX, I.G., NUNN, A.D. & HARVEY, J.P. (2001) Quantitative sampling of 0-group fish populations in large lowland rivers: point abundance sampling by electric fishing versus micromesh seine netting. *Archiv für Hydrobiologie* 151, 369–382.
- DIXON, W. & CHISWELL, B. (1996) Review of aquatic monitoring program design. *Water Research* 30, 1935–1948.
- DOWNES, B.J., BARMUTA, L.A., FAIRWEATHER, P.G., FAITH, D.P., KEOUGH, M.J., LAKE, P.S., MAPSTONE, B. & QUINN, G.P. (2002) *Monitoring Ecological Impacts: Concepts and Practice in Flowing Waters*. Cambridge University Press, New York.
- DUKERSCHEIN, J.T., BARTELS, A.D., ICKES, B.S. & PEARSON, M.S. (2011) Are two systemic fish

- assemblage sampling programmes on the upper Mississippi River telling us the same thing? *River Research and Applications* 29, 79–89.
- ELLIOTT, J.M. (1984) Numerical Changes and Population Regulation in Young Migratory Trout *Salmo trutta* in a Lake District Stream, 1966–83. *The Journal of Animal Ecology* 53, 327–350.
- FAO (2016) *The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2016*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome.
- GARCÍA-BERTHOU, E., ALCARAZ, C., BENEJAM, L. & BENITO, J. (2009) Diseño experimental y análisis de datos. In *Conceptos y técnicas de ecología fluvial* (eds A. ELOSEGI & S. SABATER), pp. 397–412. Fundación BBVA, Spain.
- GOLDSMITH, B. (1991) *Monitoring for Conservation and Ecology*. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht.
- HARVEY, J.P., NOBLE, R.A., NUNN, A.D., TAYLOR, R.J. & COWX, I.G. (2010) Monitoring sea lamprey *Petromyzon marinus* Ammocoetes in SAC rivers: a case study on the River Wye. In *Conservation Monitoring in Freshwater Habitats* (eds C. HURFORD, M. SCHNEIDER & I. COWX), pp. 193–206. Springer, Dordrecht.
- VAN HAVERBEKE, D.R., STONE, D.M., COGGINS, L.G. & PILLOW, M.J. (2013) Long-term monitoring of an endangered desert fish and factors influencing population dynamics. *Journal of Fish and Wildlife Management* 4, 163–177.
- HAXTON, T. (2011) Depth selectivity and spatial distribution of juvenile lake sturgeon in a large, fragmented river. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology* 27, 45–52.
- HEATH, D.D., BUSCH, C., KELLY, J. & ATAGI, D.Y. (2002) Temporal change in genetic structure and effective population size in steelhead trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*). *Molecular Ecology* 11, 197–214.
- HELLAWELL, J.M. (1991) Development of a rationale for monitoring. In *Monitoring for Conservation and Ecology* (ed B. GOLDSMITH), pp. 1–14. Chapman & Hall, London.
- HESTHAGEN, T., BERGER, H.M., LARSEN, B.M. & SAKSGARD, R. (1995) Monitoring fish stocks in relation to acidification in Norwegian watersheds. *Water, Air, & Soil Pollution* 85, 641–646.
- HURFORD, C. (2010) Conservation monitoring in freshwater habitats: an introduction. In *Conservation Monitoring in Freshwater Habitats* (eds C. HURFORD, M. SCHNEIDER & I. COWX), pp. 3–13. Springer, Dordrecht.
- HURFORD C., SCHNEIDER, M. & COWX, I.G. (2010) *Biological Monitoring in Freshwater Habitats*. Springer Science & Business Media, Dordrecht, Heidelberg, London, New York.
- JACKSON, D.A., PERES-NETO, P.R. & OLDEN, J.D. (2001) What controls who is where in freshwater fish communities – the roles of biotic, abiotic, and spatial factors. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences* 58, 157–170.
- JANÁČ, M., ROCHE, K., ŠLAPANSKÝ, L., POLAČIK, M. & JURAJDA, P. (2018) Long-term monitoring of native bullhead and invasive gobiids in the Danubian rip-rap zone. *Hydrobiologia* 807, 263–275.
- JURAJDA, P., SLAVÍK, O., WHITE, S. & ADÁMEK, Z. (2010) Young-of-the-year fish assemblages as an alternative to adult fish monitoring for ecological quality evaluation of running waters. *Hydrobiologia* 644, 89–101.
- KALLER, M.D., KELSO, W.E. & TREXLER, J.C. (2013) Wetland fish monitoring and assessment. In *Wetland Techniques* (eds J. ANDERSON & C. DAVIS), pp. 197–263. Springer, Dordrecht.
- KINCAID, T.M. & OLSEN, A.R. (2016) *spsurvey: Spatial Survey Design and Analysis*. <https://cran.r-project.org/package=spsurvey>.
- KRISTENSEN, E.A., BAATTRUP-PEDERSEN, A. & ANDERSEN, H.E. (2012) Prediction of stream fish assemblages from land use characteristics: implications for cost-effective design of monitoring programmes. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 184, 1435–1448.
- LARSEN, D.P., KINCAID, T.M., JACOBS, S.E. & URQUHART, N.S. (2001) Designs for evaluating local and regional scale trends. *BioScience* 51, 1069–1078.
- LINDENMAYER, D.B. & LIKENS, G.E. (2009) Adaptive monitoring: a new paradigm for long-term research and monitoring. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 24, 482–486.
- LINDENMAYER, D.B. & LIKENS, G.E. (2010) The science and application of ecological monitoring. *Biological Conservation* 143, 1317–1328.
- LOHNER, T.W. & DIXON, D.A. (2013) The value of long-term environmental monitoring programs: an Ohio River case study. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 185, 9385–9396.
- LOVETT, G.M., BURNS, D. A, DRISCOLL, C.T., JENKINS, J.C., MITCHELL, M.J., RUSTAD, L., SHANLEY, J.B., LIKENS, G.E. & HAEUBER, R. (2007) Who needs environmental monitoring?

- Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 5, 253–260.
- LOWE, W.H., LIKENS, G.E. & POWER, M.E. (2006) Linking Scales in Stream Ecology. *BioScience* 56, 591–597.
- LUNDQVIST, H., LEONARDSSON, K., CARLSSON, U., LARSSON, S., NILSSON, J., ÖSTERGREN, J., KARLSSON, L., RIVINOJA, P., SERRANO, I., PALM, D. & FERGUSON, J. (2010) Monitoring juvenile atlantic salmon and sea trout in the River Sävarån, Northern Sweden. In *Conservation Monitoring in Freshwater Habitats* (eds C. HURFORD, M. SCHNEIDER & I.G. COWX), pp. 207–218. Springer Science & Business Media, Dordrecht, Heidelberg, London, New York.
- MANN, R.H.K. & WELTON, S.J. (1995) *Eel Stock Assessment in the UK*. Institute of Freshwater Ecology, Huntingdon.
- MAXWELL, D. & JENNINGS, S. (2005) Power of monitoring programmes to detect decline and recovery of rare and vulnerable fish. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 42, 25–37
- MCCLELLAND, M.A. & SASS, G.G. (2012) Assessing fish collections from random and fixed site sampling methods on the Illinois River. *Journal of Freshwater Ecology* 27, 325–333.
- MCDONALD-MADDEN, E., BAXTER, P.W.J., FULLER, R.A., MARTIN, T.G., GAME, E.T., MONTAMBAULT, J. & POSSINGHAM, H.P. (2010) Monitoring does not always count. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 25, 547–550.
- MIHOUB, J.-B., HENLE, K., TITEUX, N., BROTONS, L., BRUMMITT, N.A. & SCHMELLER, D.S. (2017) Setting temporal baselines for biodiversity: the limits of available monitoring data for capturing the full impact of anthropogenic pressures. *Scientific Reports* 7, 41591.
- MUELLER, M., PANDER, J. & GEIST, J. (2014) A new tool for assessment and monitoring of community and ecosystem change based on multivariate abundance data integration from different taxonomic groups. *Environmental Systems Research* 3, 12.
- NICHOLS, J. & WILLIAMS, B. (2006) Monitoring for conservation. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 21, 668–673.
- NUNN, A.D., HARVEY, J.P., BRITTON, J.R., FREAR, P.A. & COWX, I.G. (2007) Fish, climate and the Gulf Stream: The influence of abiotic factors on the recruitment success of cyprinid fishes in lowland rivers. *Freshwater Biology* 52, 1576–1586.
- OBERDORFF, T., GUÉGAN, J.-F. & HUGUENY, B. (1995) Global scale patterns of fish species richness in rivers. *Ecography* 18, 345–352.
- OZMEN, M., GÜNGÖRDÜ, A., KUCUKBAY, F.Z. & GÜLER, R.E. (2006) Monitoring the effects of water pollution on *Cyprinus carpio* in Karakaya dam lake, Turkey. *Ecotoxicology* 15, 157–169.
- PONT, D., HUGUENY, B., BEIER, U., GOFFAUX, D., MELCHER, A., NOBLE, R., ROGERS, C., ROSET, N. & SCHMUTZ, S. (2006) Assessing river biotic condition at a continental scale: A European approach using functional metrics and fish assemblages. *Journal of Applied Ecology* 43, 70–80.
- POPE, K.L., LOCHMANN, S.E. & YOUNG, M.K. (2010) Methods for assessing fish populations. In *Inland fisheries management in North America* (eds W.A. HUBERT & M.C. QUIST), pp. 325–351. American Fisheries Society.
- POSSINGHAM, H., BALL, I. & ANDELMAN, S. (2000) Mathematical methods for identifying representative reserve networks. In *Quantitative Methods for Conservation Biology* (eds S. FERSON & M. BURGMAN), pp. 291–306. Springer, New York.
- QUINN, G.P. & KEOUGH, M.J. (2002) *Experimental Design and Data Analysis for Biologists*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- RADINGER, J., HÖLKER, F., HORKÝ, P., SLAVÍK, O., DENDONCKER, N. & WOLTER, C. (2016) Synergistic and antagonistic interactions of future land use and climate change on river fish assemblages. *Global Change Biology* 22, 1505–1522.
- ROWELL, T.A. (2010) Options for planning management. In *Conservation Monitoring in Freshwater Habitats* (eds C. HURFORD, M. SCHNEIDER & I. COWX), pp. 15–22. Springer, Dordrecht.
- SCARDI, M., TANCIONI, L. & CATAUDELLA, S. (2006) Monitoring methods based on fish. In *Biological Monitoring of Rivers: Applications and Perspectives* (eds G. ZIGLIO, M. SILIGARDI & G. FLAIM), pp. 135–153. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd., London.
- SOUTHWORTH, G.R., PETERSON, M.J., ROY, W.K. & MATHEWS, T.J. (2011) Monitoring fish contaminant responses to abatement actions: factors that affect recovery. *Environmental Management* 47, 1064–1076.
- STEVENS, D.L. & OLSEN, A.R. (2003) Variance estimation for spatially balanced samples of environmental resources. *Environmetrics* 14, 593–610.

- STEVENS, D.L. & OLSEN, A.R. (2004) Spatially balanced sampling of natural resources. *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 99, 262–278.
- STROBL, R.O. & ROBILLARD, P.D. (2008) Network design for water quality monitoring of surface freshwaters: A review. *Journal of Environmental Management* 87, 639–648.
- TELCI, I.T., NAM, K., GUAN, J. & ARAL, M.M. (2009) Optimal water quality monitoring network design for river systems. *Journal of Environmental Management* 90, 2987–2998.
- THORP, J.H., THOMS, M.C. & DELONG, M.D. (2006) The riverine ecosystem synthesis: Biocomplexity in river networks across space and time. *River Research and Applications* 22, 123–147.
- TRIM, A.H. & MARCUS, J.M. (1990) Integration of long-term fish kill data with ambient water quality monitoring data and application to water quality management. *Environmental Management* 14, 389–396.
- VILÀ, M. & GARCÍA-BERTHOUS, E. (2010) Monitoring biological invasions in freshwater habitats. In *Conservation Monitoring in Freshwater Habitats* (eds C. HURFORD, M. SCHNEIDER & I. COWX), pp. 91–100. Springer, Dordrecht.
- WEST, R. (2010) Shad monitoring in the Afon Tywi SAC: a case study. In *Conservation Monitoring in Freshwater Habitats* (eds C. HURFORD, M. SCHNEIDER & I. COWX), pp. 219–230. Springer, Dordrecht.
- WILDE, G.R. & FISHER, W.L. (1996) Reservoir fisheries sampling and experimental design. *American Fisheries Society Symposium Series* 16, 397–409.
- WILDHABER, M.L., HOLAN, S.H., BRYAN, J.L., GLADISH, D.W. & ELLERSIECK, M. (2011) Assessing power of large river fish monitoring programs to detect population changes: The Missouri river sturgeon example. *Journal of Applied Ichthyology* 27, 282–290.